

THE Z-CRITERION FOR COMPOSITE MATERIAL FRACTURE ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

In this work, a new mixed mode energy-based fracture hypothesis referred to as the Z-criterion is proposed for orthotropic composite material structures. The new theory predicts critical crack propagation conditions and the crack propagation direction. It is an extension of the well-known strain energy density criterion (S-criterion). The Z-criterion extends earlier strain energy criteria and removes certain deficiencies by considering separately the dilatational and distortional strain energy density factors. The new criterion is then evaluated for several composites in relatively simple configurations, and these results are compared to the predictions of other criteria.

INTRODUCTION

There are many crack initiation criteria currently available. These include the critical stress intensity factor criterion (SIF), critical energy release rate criterion, the maximum circumferential stress criterion, the crack opening displacement (COD) criterion, the J integral criterion, and the strain energy density factor criterion or S-criterion. Each of these fracture criteria is supported by many experiments. However, under certain special conditions, each may be found to be unsatisfactory.

In this work, a new strain energy-based mixed mode fracture hypothesis referred to as the Z-criterion is proposed and developed for orthotropic composite material structures. The new criterion is an extension of the S-Criterion [1-3] and predicts critical crack propagation conditions and the crack propagation direction. The new theory removes certain deficiencies by considering separately the dilatational and distortional strain energy density factors. Analytical equations have been presented for the crack tip stress fields as well as the total, dilatational, and distortional strain energy density factors for an orthotropic material (modeled as homogeneous) with an arbitrary angle between the crack direction and the unidirectional fiber orientation. The new criterion is also evaluated for several composites under Mode I loading, and these results are compared to the predictions of other criteria.

THE STRAIN ENERGY DENSITY FACTOR (S-FACTOR)

For a crack in a linear elastic body, the strain energy density factor (S-factor) is defined by

$$S = r \frac{dW}{dV} = \frac{r}{2} \sigma_{ij} \epsilon_{ij} \quad (1)$$

where W is the strain energy function of the body, dW/dV is the strain energy density function of the elastic material composing the body, r is the radial coordinate very near the crack tip, and σ_{ij} and ϵ_{ij} are the components of the cartesian stress and strain tensors, respectively.

The S-criterion as presented by Sih, et al [1-3] proposes that the strain energy density factor is the critical parameter controlling crack growth. It has been widely utilized and has introduced the prospect of analyzing crack growth problems using a single parameter. Several prior investigations have indicated that it can be successfully applied to explain the fracture behavior of homogeneous isotropic media. Also, it has been applied to a limited degree to composite materials [3]. However, no theory has been widely accepted for composite materials when they are modeled as a homogeneous anisotropic medium.

CRACK TIP STRESS FIELDS AND CALCULATION OF THE S-FACTOR

A thin off-axis orthotropic material (plane stress) with a crack subjected to Mode I loading is shown in Figure 1. The z-axis is a principal material direction and angle α is the arbitrary angle between the crack direction (along the x-axis) and the unidirectional fiber orientation. The crack tip stress fields in this case were originally presented by Sih, Paris, and Irwin [4]. They are

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_x &= \frac{K_I}{\sqrt{2r}} \operatorname{Re} \left[\frac{\mu_1 \mu_2}{\mu_1 - \mu_2} \left(\frac{\mu_2}{\sqrt{(\cos\theta + \mu_2 \sin\theta)}} - \frac{\mu_1}{\sqrt{(\cos\theta + \mu_1 \sin\theta)}} \right) \right] \\ \sigma_y &= \frac{K_I}{\sqrt{2r}} \operatorname{Re} \left[\frac{1}{\mu_1 - \mu_2} \left(\frac{\mu_1}{\sqrt{(\cos\theta + \mu_2 \sin\theta)}} - \frac{\mu_2}{\sqrt{(\cos\theta + \mu_1 \sin\theta)}} \right) \right] \\ \tau_{xy} &= \frac{K_I}{\sqrt{2r}} \operatorname{Re} \left[\frac{\mu_1 \mu_2}{\mu_1 - \mu_2} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{(\cos\theta + \mu_1 \sin\theta)}} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{(\cos\theta + \mu_2 \sin\theta)}} \right) \right]\end{aligned}\quad (2)$$

where K_I is the Mode I stress intensity factor, and r and θ are radial and angular coordinates, respectively. The constants μ_1 , μ_2 , μ_3 , and μ_4 are the so-called complex material constants which are the roots of the characteristic equation

$$\bar{a}_{11} \mu^4 - 2\bar{a}_{16} \mu^3 + (2\bar{a}_{12} + \bar{a}_{66}) \mu^2 - 2\bar{a}_{26} \mu + \bar{a}_{22} = 0 \quad (3)$$

where coefficients \bar{a}_{ij} are the elements of the off-axis compliance matrix. The compliances are related in a known manner to angle α and the orthotropic material constants E_1 , E_2 , ν_{12} , and G_{12} .

The expression in eq. (1) may be evaluated explicitly for the off-axis orthotropic material shown in Figure 1 (modeled as homogeneous) using the appropriate stress-strain relations for an off-axis orthotropic material and the crack tip stress fields given in eqs. (2). The result of this operation is

$$S = K_I^2 \Phi(\theta, \alpha, E_1, E_2, G_{12}, \nu_{12}) \quad (4)$$

where Φ is a complicated characteristic function which depends on angular position θ , the angle α between the crack direction and the unidirectional fiber orientation (1-direction), and the material properties of the orthotropic material. This characteristic function reveals a material's mechanical behavior, fracture resistance, and strain energy distribution.

DILITATIONAL AND DISTORTIONAL STRAIN ENERGY DENSITY FACTORS

The dilitational and distortional strain energy density factors are defined as

$$S_V = r \frac{dW_V}{dV} \quad , \quad S_D = r \frac{dW_D}{dV} \quad , \quad S = S_V + S_D \quad (5)$$

where dW_V/dV is the dilitational strain energy density function, dW_D/dV is the distortional strain energy density function, and r is the radial coordinate very near the crack tip. For a general linear elastic material, the dilitational strain energy density function can be calculated as

$$\frac{dW_V}{dV} = \frac{1}{2} \sigma_{ij}^V \epsilon_{ij}^V \quad (6)$$

where ϵ_{ij}^V are the dilitational strains defined as the hydrostatic state of strain causing the volume change in an infinitesimal element

$$\epsilon_{ij}^V = \left[\frac{\epsilon_x + \epsilon_y + \epsilon_z}{3} \right] \delta_{ij} \quad (7)$$

and σ_{ij}^V are the distortional stresses calculated from the distortional strain values and the appropriate linear elastic stress-strain relations. Once eq. (6) has been evaluated, the dilitational and distortional strain energy density factors can be calculated using eqs. (5).

For a general off-axis composite material (as shown in Figure 1), eq. (6) can be written in terms of the stresses as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dW_V}{dV} = \frac{1}{18} [\bar{c}_{11} + \bar{c}_{22} + \bar{c}_{33} + 2(\bar{c}_{12} + \bar{c}_{13} + \bar{c}_{23})] [(\bar{a}_{11} + \bar{a}_{12} + \bar{a}_{13})\sigma_x + \\ + (\bar{a}_{12} + \bar{a}_{22} + \bar{a}_{23})\sigma_y + (\bar{a}_{13} + \bar{a}_{23} + \bar{a}_{33})\sigma_z + (\bar{a}_{16} + \bar{a}_{26} + \bar{a}_{36})\tau_{xy}]^2 \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where coefficients \bar{a}_{ij} and \bar{c}_{ij} are the elements of the off-axis compliance and stiffness matrices, respectively. These coefficients are related in a known manner to angle α and the orthotropic material constants.

THE PROPOSED HYPOTHESIS: THE Z-CRITERION

The observation that the S-criterion was unable to correctly predict crack propagation directions in several typical composites has stimulated a search for an improved/modified strain energy based fracture criterion. The S-criterion proposes that the S-factor is the critical controlling fracture parameter irrespective of material structure or mode of fracture. For orthotropic composite materials, it is proposed that a more accurate result can be obtained by considering different controlling parameters for the different modes of fracture.

The new hypothesis presented here is based on the assumptions that Mode I fracture behavior is dominated by strength failure (dilational energy) and that Mode II fracture is dominated by elastic instability failure which causes large material distortion near the crack tip (distortional energy). In more definite terms, Mode I crack propagation is proposed to be governed by the maximum value of the dilitational strain energy density factor, and Mode II crack propagation is proposed to be governed by the minimum value of the distortional strain energy density factor. The controlling parameter in mixed mode (Modes I & II) fracture is

said to be the unweighted norm of the two individual mode governing parameters.

Mathematically, the new criterion is expressed as follows. A new multidimensional controlling parameter for composite materials fracture behavior referred to as the Z-factor is introduced

$$Z = \sqrt{Z_I^2 + Z_{II}^2} \quad (9)$$

where Z_I and Z_{II} are the Mode I and Mode II controlling parameters defined by

$$\begin{aligned} Z_I &= \text{MAX}_{(\text{WRT } \theta)} [(S_V)_I] \\ Z_{II} &= \text{MIN}_{(\text{WRT } \theta)} [(S_D)_{II}] \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

and $[(S_V)_I]$ and $[(S_D)_{II}]$ are the dilatational and distortional strain energy density factors calculated from the appropriate crack tip stress fields for Modes I and II, respectively. For pure Mode I or pure Mode II situations, the Z-factor degenerates to Z_I and Z_{II} , respectively.

Unstable crack propagation is said to occur when

$$Z \geq Z_{cr} \quad (11)$$

where Z_{cr} not a single critical value but one which depends on the value of the ratio Z_I/Z_{II} . As shown in Figure 2, a transition line (to be experimentally determined) is proposed to exist in the Z_I - Z_{II} plane which indicates the limit of crack stability. For pure Mode I conditions, crack propagation will occur when

$$(Z = Z_I) \geq (Z_I)_{cr} \quad (12)$$

where $(Z_I)_{cr}$ is the critical value of the maximum dilatational strain energy density factor. For pure Mode II conditions, crack propagation will occur when

$$(Z = Z_{II}) \geq (Z_{II})_{cr} \quad (13)$$

where $(Z_{II})_{cr}$ is the critical value of the minimum distortional strain energy density factor.

The crack propagation direction is proposed to be along vector

$$\vec{v} = A\vec{\lambda} = \frac{Z_I}{(Z_I)_{cr}} \vec{\lambda}_1 + \frac{Z_{II}}{(Z_{II})_{cr}} \vec{\lambda}_2 \quad (14)$$

where $\vec{\lambda}_1$ is a unit vector aimed in the direction where $(S_V)_I$ obtains its maximum value Z_I , and $\vec{\lambda}_2$ is a unit vector aimed in the direction where $(S_D)_{II}$ obtains its minimum value Z_{II} . This condition is shown visually in Figure 3. Note that in a single mode situation, eq. (14) predicts that crack propagation will occur in the direction where the proposed controlling parameter for that mode achieves its critical value.

It is clear that the above method has the potential to be extended to include Mode III crack configurations. This process is under consideration.

APPLICATIONS TO MODE I PROBLEMS

Several sample calculations have been undertaken to predict crack propagation directions for pure Mode I loading of composite materials and isotropic materials. The distortional and dilatational strain energy density factors were calculated by considering eqs. (4,5,8) along with the stress fields given in eqs. (2). These operations lead to results in the form

$$\begin{aligned} S_V &= (S_V)_I = K_I^2 \Phi_{VI}(\theta, E_1, E_2, \nu_{12}, G_{12}, a) \\ S_D &= (S_D)_I = K_I^2 \Phi_{DI}(\theta, E_1, E_2, \nu_{12}, G_{12}, a) \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Because of the complicated dependence of the characteristic functions of the material properties, they were not derived explicitly. Rather, they were evaluated with a computer program once specific values of the material properties and angle α were specified. Figures 4-6 contain plots for an isotropic material ($E = 46.3$ GPa, $\nu = .25$) of the angular distribution of S , S_V , and S_D , respectively. Figures 7-10 contain plots for an on-axis orthotropic material ($\alpha = 0$, $E_1 = 46.3$ GPa, $E_2 = 12.3$ GPa, $\nu_{12} = .32$, $G_{12} = 4.8$ GPa) of the angular distribution of S , S_V , and S_D , respectively. In both cases, the known experimentally observed crack growth direction is $\theta = 0^\circ$ (along the crack). It is observed that in the crack growth direction, the strain energy density factor and the distortional energy density factor both pass through minimum values for the isotropic material and maximum values for the orthotropic material. Hence, they are not consistent indicators of fracture. However, the dilatational strain energy density factor obtains a maximum in the crack growth direction for both cases and is therefore a consistent indicator (for the configurations considered). Other examples have demonstrated the same tendencies.

CONCLUSIONS

In this work, a new mixed mode energy-based fracture hypothesis referred to as the Z-criterion has been proposed for orthotropic composite material structures. The new theory predicts critical crack propagation conditions and the crack propagation direction. It is an extension of the S-criterion, and removes certain deficiencies by considering separately the dilatational and distortional strain energy density factors. The new criterion has been evaluated for several composites in relatively simple configurations and it shows potential to predict crack propagation directions in situations where other criteria fail. Further work is required to fully evaluate the accuracy of the new criterion.

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Figure 1

Figure 3

Figure 2

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 8

Figure 7

Figure 9